

Agroforestry in Slovakia

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Support for the preservation of traditional varieties of fruit trees
- Development to freedom in land management

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Slovakia		
Nut level:	-		
Eurostat code:	SK		
Area (km ²):	48.702		
Population	2018	2022	
Population	5.443.120	5.434.712	
Density (p km ⁻²)	112	112	
Cover data	2018	2022	
Forest	43,51%	17,88%	
Arable land	22,95%	37,29%	
Permanent crops	0,03%	0,23%	
Agroforestry	4,62%	5,46%	
Shrubland	3,52%	5,82%	
Grassland	18,08%	22,69%	
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022	
Silvopasture	3,07%	4,08%	
Agrisilviculture	0,00%	0,00%	
Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%	
Kitchen gardens	1,55%	1,38%	
Holding type	2016	2023	
Natural person (ha)	373.800	331.160	
Legal person (ha)	1.516.020	1.476.980	
Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	-	
Natural person (holder)	22.460	13.900	
Legal person (holder)	3.200	3.620	
Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	-	
Regional Agricultural Area	Used	2016	2023
Farm number		25.650	17.530
Farm ha (UAA)		1.889.810	1.808.140
Animal populations (Thousand head)		2018	2023
Live bovine animals		439	430
Dairy cows		128	115
Non dairy cows		67	73
Live swine, domestic species		627	403

Live sheep	351	-
Live goats	37	-
CROPS (Hectares)	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	1.889.810	1.808.140
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	757.810	696.420
Common wheat and spelt	378.980	337.660
Durum wheat	41.230	67.740
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	12.710	11.990
Barley	115.100	114.360
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	14.470	9.950
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	182.530	139.480
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	12.680	19.930
Industrial crops	256.870	275.600
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	8.170	8.240
Fibre crops	-	110
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	3.100	4.450
Plants harvested green from arable land	233.810	178.030
Green maize	79.100	59.990
Kitchen gardens	420	270

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	7
Forestry	4
Crop diversification including woody perennials	6
Crop rotation including woody perennials	4
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	1
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	2
Interventions	7

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